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THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE ROLE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR

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abstract

The article analyzes the concept of the service sector as an economic category. The role of the service sector in the economy of the countries of the world and Uzbekistan is analyzed. Trends in the development of the service sector in 2017-2022 have been fully studied by the main types. The dynamics of enterprises and organizations working in this field in recent years has been analyzed. Prospects for further development of the service sector are highlighted.

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Introduction

Over the years of independence, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in the development of the economy, in particular the service sector. This sector in our country is becoming more and more diversified and there is a high growth of certain types of services.

In general, the service sector in Uzbekistan demonstrates promising dynamics with the widest opportunities for further growth and development. The Government's efforts to support this sector of the economy, including investments in infrastructure, as well as financial incentives and favorable conditions for doing business, are likely to continue to contribute to its intensive growth in the coming years.

Research methodology

The article uses methods of logical thinking, logical analysis as a theoretical and methodological basis; decrees adopted by President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev on the development of the national economy, as well as scientific and methodological

literature on the research topic. The data of the Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics were used as an information base.

Results

The service sector plays an important role in the economic growth of the country, creating cheap jobs, providing employment and reducing poverty. According to the calculations of the International Labor Organization, an increase in the service sector by 1% reduces the poverty level by an average of 1.5%. This is especially important for our country, whose population and labor resources are increasing day by day.

An important pattern of economic development around the world is the relationship between economic growth and the increasing role of services in the national economy, which is reflected in the increasing share of labor, material and financial resources used in the service sector.

With the development of society and the growth of productive forces, there is a certain development of this sphere. There is an increase in employment, an increase in the technical equipment of labor, the introduction of more and more advanced technologies.

Currently, the role of the service sector, as one of the most important sectors of the economy, is very large and relevant. This is, in particular, due to the complexity of production, the saturation of the market with goods of both everyday and individual demand, the rapid growth of scientific and technological progress, which leads to innovations in the life of society.

The service sector is very multifaceted and it includes various types of activities that help to increase labor productivity and achieve production efficiency. The final result of such activity is not a finished product, but the provision of services that can be provided not only to enterprises, but also to individuals – end consumers.

Today, the service sector is one of the three largest economic spheres. Thus, according to the results of a World Bank study, the United States is one of the largest economies in the world and has a well-developed service sector. In 2021, this sector (value added) accounted for 77.6% 1) of the country's GDP.

In 2021, the value added of the service sector in GDP (Figure 1) of Switzerland was 71.92% 1), Great Britain - 71.46% 1), France - 70.34% 1), Australia – 65.65% 1), Germany - 62.88% 1), Brazil – 59.38% 1), China – 53.31 % 1), Russia – 52.91% 1).

Figure 1. The share of the service sector in the GDP of the countries of the world in 2021 (in%)

Source: The Global Economy (<https://ru.theglobaleconomy.com>)

In Uzbekistan, the share of added value of services in 2021 in GDP was 39.6%, and according to preliminary data for 2022 - 41.5%.

In many developed and developing countries, the service sector accounts for more than 50% of the employed population. In Uzbekistan, this figure was 51.0% in 2021.

In recent years, large-scale work to create decent living conditions for the population, improve the business environment, provide employment by supporting the socio-economic development of the country, active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and creative potential has led to an increase in the number of enterprises operating in the service sector.

During the implementation of the main tasks and directions for the development of the service sector in the republic, in 2017-2022, the volume of market services increased 1.9 times and reached 357.6 trillion soums. The volume of services rendered per capita during this period increased by 1.7 times and amounted to 10.0 million soums.

The dynamics of the development of the service sector for 2017-2022 indicates positive trends in the development of the main types of services (Table 1).

Table 1.

Dynamics of the volume of market services rendered according to the Service Sector Development Program for 2017-2022, billion soums

	2017-2022	*	Real growth rate
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			compared to 2017, times
Services - total	118 811.0	357 554.5	1.9
including by type:			3.0
Communication and information services	8 196.7	22 917.6	5.1
Financial services	15 023.8	80 431.0	1.5
Transport services	36 217.2	81 006.6	1.4
including: motor transport services	20 232.9	41 318.3	1.6
Accommodation and catering services	3 649.6	11 322.8	1.4
Trade services	32 006.9	88 847.9	1.5
Real estate related services	4 026.5	9 674.3	2.3
Education services	4 402.0	15 395.7	2.1
Healthcare services	1 701.5	6 384.2	1.5
Rental and rental services	2 589.2	6 444.3	1.4
Computer and household goods repair services	2 329.2	5 842.3	1.3
Individual services	3 134.4	8 713.9	2.0
Architecture, engineering surveys, technical testing and analysis services	1 611.7	7 338.2	2.1
Other services	3 922.3	13 235.7	1.9

In recent years, the information technology (IT) sector has been developing rapidly in Uzbekistan. Investments are actively attracted in the republic for the development of ICT infrastructure, including for the expansion of broadband Internet access services and the construction of new data processing centers. In 2017-2022, the total volume of communication and information services has tripled. By the end of 2022, the volume of communication and information services was fixed at the level of 22.9 trillion soums. Compared to 2017, it increased by 14.7 trillion soums.

In the Uzbek market, cellular communication services are provided by such companies as LLC "Unitel" (Beeline trademark), LLC "Universal Mobile Systems" (UMS trademark), JV "RWC" (Perfectum Mobile trademark), IP LLC "Coscom" (Ucell trademark), LLC "Humans" (trademark "Humans") and a branch of UzMobile AK "Uzbektelecom".

Another important part of the service sector in Uzbekistan is the financial sector. The country is developing its banking sector by introducing new financial products and services, as well as improving access to finance. The Government of the Republic is working to attract foreign investment in the financial sector, which has helped to bring new technologies and accumulated experience here, contributing to the modernization of the financial sector. Thus, in 2017-2022, the volume of financial services increased 5.1 times. In 2022, the volume of financial services reached 80.4 trillion soums. Compared to 2017 (15.0 trillion sum), an increase in the volume of financial services for 2022 by 65.4 trillion soums was noted.

In 2017-2022, the volume of transport services increased by 1.5 times. So, in 2022, their volume, compared with 2017 (36.2 trillion. sum), increased by 44.8 trillion. sum and reached 81.0 trillion. sum, or amounted to 22.7% of the total volume of market services rendered.

Trade services form a significant part of the total volume of services rendered in the economy (88.8 trillion soums), having increased, in general, by 56.8 trillion over the period from 2017 to 2022.sum, or 1.4 times.

In 2017-2022, the growth of services related to the field of education was also recorded by 2.3 times. For example, in 2022, the volume of services in the field of education, compared with 2017 (4.4 trillion. sum), increased by 11.0 trillion. sum and reached 15.4 trillion. sum, or amounted to 4.3% of the total volume of market services rendered (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Growth rates of educational services

Source stat.uz

Currently, there are 191 institutes and universities operating on the territory of Uzbekistan, including 28 foreign ones. They train 1,040,4 thousand people. In 2017-2022, their number increased by 742.7 thousand people.

Compared to 2017, the volume of healthcare services increased by 4.7 trillion in 2022. sum and became equal to 6.4 trillion. sum. In the total volume of services, their share was 1.8%.

Currently, over 1.2 thousand hospitals operate throughout the republic. The number of private medical institutions in Uzbekistan is growing, which creates healthy competition in the field of medicine, allowing to improve the quality of medical services provided to the population and reduce prices for them.

In 2022, the volume of services provided by small businesses was equal to 173.2 trillion. sum (for 2017 – 69.2 trillion. sum) and in the total volume of market services produced, their share was 48.4%.

Currently, new types of services are actively developing in Uzbekistan, their importance for regional economies has increased markedly, primarily in urban agglomerations.

Today, electronic banking and online shopping are an integral part of our lives. In the modern information world, as a result of the widespread use of the Internet, logistics, the emergence of electronic payment systems and electronic document management, a new form of activity is actively developing – e-commerce. The COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020 led to an acceleration of digital transformation. Digital solutions have become a tool that allows people and businesses to continue part of their economic and social activities remotely. This has led to increased use of remote work, video conferencing, digital entertainment and other applications. It also caused a sharp increase in e-commerce.

The share of e-commerce in gross value added increased from 0.03% in 2018 to 0.57% in 2021.

With the appearance of new types of services on the market, it became necessary to monitor them for more complete and high-quality accounting.

In 2021, the volume of dispatcher services, including services for the provision of orders to drivers (for example, the provision of transportation orders) amounted to 41.8 billion. sum, their share of the total volume of warehousing and auxiliary transport services (5 380.4 billion sum) is marked at the level of 0.8%.

The volume of catering services (catering is a comprehensive catering service at remote locations) for 2021 was equal to 23.7 billion. sum, or 0.3% of the total volume of rendered market services for the provision of food and beverages (7 111.9 billion sum).

Conclusion

Thus, the service sector is becoming an increasingly important part of Uzbekistan's economy and in 2022 it accounted for almost half of the country's GDP. Various types of services, such as transport, financial and ICT services, are growing rapidly thanks to significant investments and government support. As our country continues to diversify the national economy and invest in its development of the service sector, there are many opportunities for its further growth and expansion.

References:

1. Kotler Ph., Keller K. Marketing – Management. – 14th Ed. – NJ: Prentice Hall, 2012.
2. Bell D. The coming of post-industrial society: A venture of social forecasting. – NY: Basic Books, 1973.
3. Цой Марина Петровна, & Ибрагимов Зиёдулло Ташмуратович. (2022). ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ЦИФРОВОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. *International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research*, 1(2), 339–342. Retrieved from <https://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/196>
4. Национальная база данных законодательной информации Республики Узбекистан: <https://lex.uz/>
5. Веб-сайт Агентство статистики при Президенте Республики Узбекистан: <https://stat.uz/>
6. Веб-сайт Департамента статистики по экономическим и социальным вопросам ООН: <https://unstats.un.org>
7. Веб-сайт Межгосударственный статистический комитет содружества независимых государств: <http://new.cisstat.org>
8. The Global Economy <https://ru.theglobaleconomy.com>
9. Веб-сайт статистическая служба Европейского союза: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
10. Kamolov, Dostonbek Rustam O'G'Li. "O'ZBEKISTONDA DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI." *Academic research in educational sciences* 3.NUU Conference 2 (2022): 348-352.